

Regiospecific 1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition Polymerization of Keto-Stabilized Bisalkylidenephosphoranes with Bisazides*

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Thermostable poly-1,2,3-triazoles (7) were prepared by the regiospecific reaction of bisazides with keto-stabilized bisalkylidenephosphoranes (6) in DMSO solution. In spectroscopic analysis revealed the presence of terminal ylide functions in all polymeric samples and also azide functions in most of them, especially in the lower molecular weight fractions. The novel bisylides required in this work were prepared by two reaction routes, previously elaborated on for monofunctional systems. The first method consists of reacting bisacyl chlorides with 4 equiv. of alkylidenephosphoranes in benzene solution. The second method involves treatment of bithioesters with two equiv. of alkylidenephosphoranes in refluxing toluene.

Thermostable poly-1,2,3-triazoles have been recently prepared by 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition polymerization of the following systems : (i) azidoacetylenes¹, and (ii) bisacetylenes with bisazides². In both cases, however, the cycloadditions were non-regiospecific³, producing polymers which contained a mixture of 1,4- and 1,5-disubstituted triazole rings.

*Dedicated to Prof. Santi R. Palit on the occasion of his 60th birth day anniversary.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The novel bisylides $\underline{6a-d}$ used in this work were prepared by the transylidation method⁶ according to the equation :

This method, however, failed for the synthesis of those bisylides ($\underline{6e-g}$) which contain a methylene group (instead of a phenylene group) in α -position to the CO function, the bisylides $\underline{6e-g}$ being isolated in only 2% yield. Instead, dark resinous products were mainly obtained, presumably formed by dehydrochlorination of the acyl chlorides and further polymerization of the resulting ketenes⁷. In order to obtain compounds $\underline{6e-g}$ in reasonable yields, the following elegant sequence, discovered by Bestmann⁸, was utilized :

TABLE I

Keto-stabilized bisalkylidenephosphoranes (6)

N°	R ⁴	R ⁵	Yield %	Recrystn solvent	Mp
$\underline{6a}$	Ph	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄	69	toluene	295.5-296
$\underline{6b}$	H	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄	61	MeOH	> 360
$\underline{6c}$	Et	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄	44	CH ₂ Cl ₂ -ether	230-232
$\underline{6d}$	Et	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ O(CH ₂) ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ (<i>m</i>)	60	MeOH-H ₂ O	194-198
$\underline{6e}$	H	(CH ₂) ₃	42	MeOH-H ₂ O	182-183
$\underline{6f}$	H	(CH ₂) ₄	19	MeOH-H ₂ O	210-213
$\underline{6g}$	H	(CH ₂) ₆	53	MeOH-H ₂ O	234-238

A few comments on solubility properties of the bisylides ($\underline{6a-g}$) are necessary here. Compounds $\underline{6a}$ and $\underline{6b}$ were not sufficiently soluble and therefore unsuitable for polymerization experiments. The solubility was greatly increased by introducing an ether function into the molecule ($\underline{6d}$) or by replacing the phenylene group by a polymethylene group ($\underline{6e-g}$). Compounds $\underline{6c}$ and $\underline{6d}$, having an ethyl function at position R⁴, were intentionally prepared to increase the electron-density on the C = C bond of the ylide, and, hence, to increase the

reactivity of the bisylide⁴. Selected examples from table 1 were reacted with aromatic bisazides in DMSO solution and the polymerizations were monitored by ir (N_3 at 2130 cm^{-1}). After completion of the reaction, the soluble and insoluble fractions were collected and characterized. The results are summarized in table 2. Molecular weight determination of the soluble fraction of $\tilde{7e}$ furnished a value of 1916, corresponding to only 5 units. This oligomer showed the presence of both the azide (2100 cm^{-1}) and ylide functions (540 cm^{-1}) in the ir spectrum, but did not further polymerize, even on continued heating in HMPA at 80° for 4 days. The molecular weights of the insoluble fractions could not be determined, but are also believed to be low because the ir spectra exhibited weak ylide absorptions and in many cases also weak azide absorptions (see table 2).

Samples of insoluble polymer fractions were subjected to thermal gravimetric analysis under nitrogen, and, as expected, were found to be stable up to 350° . The results of two typical polymers, i.e., with and without a terminal azide function, are shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE 2
Poly-1,2,3-triazoles ($\tilde{7}$)

N ^o	R ¹	R ⁴	R ⁵	Reaction conditions	% Conversion* by ir	Insoluble fraction			Soluble fraction		
						%	azide/ylide present by ir		%	azide/ylide present by ir.	
$\tilde{7a}$	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄	t	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄	5 days at 80°	86	17	—	+	4	+	+
$\tilde{7b}$	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄	Et	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄	2 days at 100°	94	27	—	+			
$\tilde{7c}$	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄	H	(CH ₂) ₃	24 hr at 80°	99				42	+	+
$\tilde{7d}$	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄	H	(CH ₂) ₃	24 hr at 80°	97	25	—	+	51	+	+
$\tilde{7e}$	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OC ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i>)	H	(CH ₂) ₃	36 hr at 80°	98	20	—	+	46	+	+
$\tilde{7f}$	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄	H	(CH ₂) ₆	48 hr at 80°	98	59	+	+	14	+	+
$\tilde{7g}$	<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄	H	(CH ₂) ₆	48 hr at 80°	96	23	+	+			
$\tilde{7h}$	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ OC ₆ H ₄ (<i>p</i>)	H	(CH ₂) ₆	48 hr at 80°	94				55	+	+

* Based on the decrease of the ir N_3 absorption peak at about 2100 cm^{-1} during the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points were obtained on a Leitz apparatus and are uncorrected. The molecular weight of compound $\tilde{7e}$ was measured with a Mechrolab vapor-pressure osmometer, model 301A. Thermal gravimetric analyses were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer TGS-1

thermobalance. The bisylides $\tilde{6a-h}$ were prepared according to the general procedures reported for monofunctional systems⁶. Their structures were ascertained by ir and nmr spectral analysis, and by microanalyses :

$\tilde{6a}$,	Calcd for $C_{58}H_{44}O_2P_2$ (834) : C, 83.45; H, 5.28; P, 7.43. Found : C, 83.88; H, 5.31; P, 7.17.
$\tilde{6c}$,	Calcd for $C_{50}H_{44}O_2P_2$ (738) : C, 81.30; H, 5.94; P, 8.40. Found : C, 81.21; H, 5.84; P, 8.24.
$\tilde{6d}$,	Calcd for $C_{59}H_{54}O_4P_2$ (888) : C, 79.73; H, 6.08; P, 6.98. Found : C, 76.79 ; H, 6.20; P, 6.80.
$\tilde{6e}$,	Calcd for $C_{43}H_{38}O_2P_2$ (648) : C, 79.63; H, 5.86, P, 9.57. Found : C, 79.70; H, 5.90; P, 9.80.
$\tilde{6f}$,	Calcd for $C_{44}H_{40}O_2P_2$ (662) : C, 79.76; H, 6.04; P, 9.36. Found : C, 79.60; H, 6.02; P, 9.45.
$\tilde{6g}$,	Calcd for $C_{46}H_{42}O_2P_2$ (690) : C, 80.00; H, 6.38; P, 8.99. Found : C, ; H, 6.45; P, 9.05.†

General Procedure for the synthesis of the Poly-1,2,3-triazoles (7)

Equimolar amounts (1 mmole) of bisazide and bisylide were allowed to react in dry DMSO (10 ml) at the appropriate temperature (*see table 2*). The reactions were followed by recording the decrease of the ir N_3 stretching vibration at about 2100 cm^{-1} . The

Fig. 4. Thermal gravimetric analyses of $\tilde{7a}$ and $\tilde{7f}$ under nitrogen

precipitate was collected, washed with solvent, dried and characterized. The mother liquor was poured into water; the precipitate washed with water and hot methanol (to eliminate OPPh_3), and dried. Ir spectral analyses (KBr) of the soluble and insoluble fractions all showed the presence of small peaks at 540 cm^{-1} , attributed to the Ph-P vibration. Several samples also exhibited small azide vibrations at about 2100 cm^{-1} . Furthermore, the soluble and insoluble fractions displayed similar absorption patterns with typical triazole peaks⁹ at about 1250 (medium or strong), 1110 (weak or medium), 1080 (weak or medium) and 980 cm^{-1} (medium or strong).

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